

ISic4354

I.Sicily inscription 4354

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2016.05.12

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

via Orto San Clemente, excavation of November 1968

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo di Archeologia
dell'Universita di Catania, inventory 05/398

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Biondi, G., Buscemi Felici, G. 2014. Iscrizioni. In Biondi, G., Buscemi Felici, G., Tortorici, E.(eds.), *Il museo archeologico dell'Università di Catania. Collezione Libertini*. Acireale. pp. 170-173. At 171 no.243 fig.42

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